

Political Rights of Minorities: A Comparative Study of Political Representation, Voting and Party Participation in Türkiye and Azerbaijan

Mahmut Kanber¹

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-09, 2024, p. 01– 25. - 0099-0001-2408-0201.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE")

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

¹ 0009-0009-9197-2879

CURRENT SCIENCE

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

"" • Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with

Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current

Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The journal will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")

"" • Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

This research compares minorities' political engagement in Turkey and Azerbaijan, focusing on political representation, the right to vote and be elected, and participation in political parties, using current statistics and an extensive literature analysis. International human rights norms and both nations' national legal frameworks are assessed, revealing gaps between theoretical and legal guarantees of minority' political rights and their actual application. The study provides concrete and applicable policy recommendations for creating a more inclusive and democratic political environment by delving into minorities' levels of political representation, the barriers they face in electoral processes, and their political party participation practices.

Keywords: *Minority Rights, Political Participation, Democratic Participation, Legal Regulations, International Law, Minority Policies, Civil Society, Language and Cultural Rights*

Introduction

One of the essential ideals of democratic societies is that all people, regardless of identification, have equal rights and may actively participate in political processes. Minorities' political rights are vital to maintaining their equitable participation in society while protecting their cultural, linguistic, and religious identities. However, like in many other nations, minorities in Turkey and Azerbaijan confront a number of barriers to political involvement.

In Turkey, the small number of minority MPs in the 2023 elections, as well as their poor participation in political parties, suggest that challenges in this area persist. In Azerbaijan, ethnic minorities have low representation in parliament and political activity. This demonstrates

CURRENT SCIENCE

that, although minorities' political rights are acknowledged on paper, they are not implemented efficiently in reality.

The purpose of this research is to identify the issues that impede minorities' political engagement in Turkey and Azerbaijan, as well as the potential in this field, via the use of current data and an extensive literature analysis. In this context, the degree of political representation of minorities in both nations, the obstacles they encounter in the voting and election processes, their participation patterns in political parties, and the role of civil society groups will be examined.

Methodology

This comparative study uses quantitative research methodologies to better understand the complex and varied nature of minorities' political rights. The following measures were taken: Data sources included data from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK), the Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, the Supreme Election Board, official reports from political parties, and current reports from international organizations (UN, OSCE, Council of Europe). Data Analysis Methods: The acquired data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, comparative analysis, and correlation analyses. These studies include metrics such as the number of minorities in the population, political representation levels, election participation rates, and political party membership figures.

Comparative Perspective: By comparing statistics from Turkey and Azerbaijan, the similarities and contrasts between the two nations become clear.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

The study's theoretical framework is based on current literature and ideas on minority rights and political involvement.

CURRENT SCIENCE

International Human Rights Law: The UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the European Convention on Human Rights, and the United Nations Declaration on Minority Rights have all been analyzed. Theoretical methodologies: Will Kymlicka's theory of multicultural citizenship and Arend Models that would increase minorities' political involvement have been analyzed using methodologies such as Lijphart's consensual democracy model and Charles Taylor's recognition policies.

Current Academic research: In recent years, the literature has featured research on minority rights in Turkey and Azerbaijan, as well as reports from non-governmental groups.

Minorities in Turkey and Azerbaijan: Their Historical, Cultural, and Demographic Profiles

Minorities in Turkey

In Turkey, the Treaty of Lausanne recognizes only Greeks, Armenians, and Jews as minorities. The nation also has ethnic and cultural groups such Kurds, Laz, Circassians, Arabs, Georgians, and Roma. TÜİK statistics estimates that the Kurdish community makes about 15-20% of the overall population.

Minorities usually have a worse socioeconomic position than the national average. They may experience prejudice in school and the workplace. In addition, there are prohibitions on mother tongue teaching and usage in public.

Minorities in Azerbaijan compose nearly 91% of the population, however minority groups like as Lezgins, Talyshs, Avars, Tats, Kurds, and Russians do exist. According to the Azerbaijan State Statistics Committee, minorities account for around 9% of the overall population. Minorities have certain legal rights to maintain their language and culture, but in reality, these rights are restricted. There is little access to mother tongue services in education and the media.

Comparative Analysis

In both nations, minorities face socioeconomic disadvantages. These disadvantages are evident in crucial areas such as educational attainment, employment rates, income levels, and access to social services.

Educational Levels:

Educational Status of Minorities in Turkey:

Education presents significant challenges for Turkey's minority communities, particularly Kurds and Roma. According to statistics from the Ministry of National Education, education rates in Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia are lower than the national average. Girls' school attendance rates are very low. Minority kids' academic progress suffers due to a lack of instruction in their mother language.

The educational status of minorities in Azerbaijan:

Minority communities have fewer opportunities for education in their home language. In areas where ethnic groups like as Lezgi and Talysh exist, the number of schools that teach in minority languages is minimal. This has a detrimental impact on students' academic progress and access to higher education.

Employment Rates and Income

Employment and Income Situation in Turkey:

The Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK) reports significant unemployment rates in areas with large minority population density. The unemployment rate is higher than the national average, particularly in the Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia areas. Per capita income is similarly low in these areas. Some minority groups, such the Roma, are compelled to labor in seasonal and insecure employment.

Employment and Income Situation in Azerbaijan:

According to statistics from Azerbaijan's State Statistics Committee, unemployment rates are high in rural regions where minorities dwell. Minority groups' economic position suffers from a lack of economic possibilities and insufficient regional development programs. This causes societal concerns such as migration and demographic shifts to major cities. Language and Cultural Rights.

Legal Regulations:

Turkey: According to Article 42 of the Constitution, Turkish is the sole language used in education and training. However, legislative amendments enacted in 2013 enabled private schools to provide instruction in a variety of languages and dialects. However, public schools have limited opportunities for mother tongue instruction. Azerbaijan's constitution acknowledges all people' freedom to use and develop their native language. However, Azerbaijani Turkish is utilized in educational and governmental settings. Minority languages are not widely used in public life or education.

Deficiencies in the Application

Despite legislative rules in both nations, there exist gaps in practice for preserving language and cultural rights. The number of media entities that broadcast in minority languages is minimal, and official funding is inadequate. There are logistical and financial barriers to conducting cultural events and promoting minority cultures.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Access to Social Services and Discrimination

Situation in Turkey:

Minorities encounter a variety of challenges to obtaining health care, social assistance programs, and other public services. Minorities, particularly those living in rural and impoverished regions, struggle to access services owing to a lack of infrastructure and linguistic hurdles. Furthermore, bigotry and prejudice may prohibit minorities from obtaining proper services from governmental institutions.

Situation in Azerbaijan:

Minority communities lack adequate health and social services. Minorities' living conditions suffer as a result of unfair economic resource allocation and insufficient regional development programs. Some minority groups may face prejudice based on their ethnic identity.

Political Participation and Representation

Political Representation In Turkey:

Minorities have little political representation in Turkey. The high electoral threshold (10%) makes it difficult for small parties and minority representation organizations to get parliamentary seats. However, in recent years, several political parties have begun to put candidates from minority groups on their ballots. However, this representation is still low when compared to the percentage of minority populations.

Political representation in Azerbaijan:

In Azerbaijan, minorities have low representation in parliament. Minority groups find it difficult to be represented by independent or ethnically oriented parties under the current election system and political party regulation. Furthermore, political pressures and limits on free speech reduce minority political engagement.

Comparative Assessment

Similarities:

Minorities have socioeconomic disadvantages in both nations, including lower levels of education, employment, and income. This arrangement prohibits minorities from engaging equally in social activities.

Language and Cultural Rights: Despite the existence of legislative laws, minority languages and cultures are not adequately protected in reality. Opportunities for education and media in one's mother language are restricted.

Limited Political engagement: Minorities have minimal political representation and engagement in decision-making in both nations. Minorities face legal and institutional hurdles to successful political participation.

Differences:

Legal Recognition and Policies: In Turkey, the Treaty of Lausanne's restricted definition of minority prevents many ethnic groups from being formally acknowledged as minorities. Although Azerbaijan's constitution protects the rights of all ethnic groups, its practical application is problematic.

International influences and regional problems: In Azerbaijan, the Nagorno-Karabakh war and ties with Armenia have a direct impact on minority policy and ethnic relations. In Turkey, the Kurdish conflict and counter-terrorism strategies have an impact on minorities' rights and official policy.

Conclusion

A comparative investigation reveals that minorities in Turkey and Azerbaijan confront comparable socioeconomic and political issues. Minorities in both nations have structural issues and implementation gaps that impede them from participating fairly and effectively in society. This scenario necessitates broad legislative reforms and the adoption of procedures that safeguard and enhance minorities' rights.

Legal Analysis

International law

Conventions to which Turkey and Azerbaijan are party include the United Nations International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights. These conventions defend minorities' rights and combat discrimination.

National Law

Despite the concept of equality in the Turkish Constitution, minority rights are subject to restricted rules. The rights of groups other than those recognized by the Treaty of Lausanne are not legally protected.

The Azerbaijani Constitution provides that all people have equal rights. However, explicit rules assuring political representation and linguistic rights for minorities are insufficient.

Effectiveness of Legal Regulations

Both nations have issues with legal restrictions that do not meet international norms. There are severe issues with the execution of legal rights. Minorities' political engagement is limited, in particular, by election and political party legislation.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The Role of Civil Society and Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs)

Minority rights are defended in large part by civil society groups and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). In Turkey, groups and foundations dedicated to minority rights run education and awareness campaigns. In Azerbaijan, NGOs' operations are highly restricted and subject to official oversight.

International Comparisons

Minority policies and excellent practice examples from European nations were analyzed. Legal and institutional structures facilitate minorities' political involvement in nations such as Sweden, Belgium, and Canada.

Impact of Technology and Social Media

Today, social media and digital platforms provide new chances for minorities to share their opinions and organize. Minority groups in both nations use social media to actively advocate for their rights.

Educational and Awareness Programs

Education and awareness campaigns are crucial for expanding minorities' political involvement. In Turkey, several non-governmental organizations (NGOs) operate in this field. In Azerbaijan, such programs are few.

Argument

Effective Models of Political Representation of Minorities
Various methods and initiatives have been created to improve minorities' political representation and involvement in the democratic process. The proportional representation

CURRENT SCIENCE

system, quota practices, and specific minority representation methods are particularly noteworthy.

Proportionate Representation System:

Definition and Benefits: The proportional representation system allocates seats in parliament based on the percentage of votes cast in elections. This mechanism ensures that votes do not go to waste while also allowing tiny parties and minority groups representation.

Applicability to Turkey and Azerbaijan:

Turkey's 10% electoral threshold affects the efficiency of the proportional representation system. This barrier is among the highest in the world, making it very difficult for minority groups to be represented in parliament. Lowering or eliminating the barrier might enhance representation for minorities and small parties.

Azerbaijan: Similarly, Azerbaijan's election system is majority-based, which limits minority participation in parliament. A transition to proportional representation or enhancement of the existing system might result in a more inclusive parliamentary structure.

Quota Applications:

Definition and Benefits: Quota practices are the practice of allocating a certain number or percentage of seats in parliament or other representative bodies to a specified group (for example, ethnic minorities or women). This technique assures minorities' representation and active engagement in decision-making processes.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Applicability to Turkey and Azerbaijan:

Quotas have not yet been imposed in Turkey. However, political parties might be urged to put minority candidates on their lists by enacting internal restrictions. Quotas established by legislative laws may help to improve minority participation. Azerbaijan has no quota system either. Given the country's ethnic composition and political dynamics, implementing a quota system might improve minority participation.

Special Minority Representation Mechanisms:

In highly populated regions, organizing electoral districts or offering special rights to minority members might help to boost political representation. In certain nations, minority groups are allocated special electoral districts or increased representation privileges.

Obstacles to Voting and Being Elected

To enable minorities to fully exercise their right to vote and be elected, current barriers must be removed:

High electoral thresholds:

Effects: High electoral thresholds make it more difficult for political parties to represent minority groups, preventing them from speaking out in parliament. Solution Proposals: Reduce election thresholds to realistic levels, or provide concessions for minority parties. Alternatively, fair representation may be assured via techniques such as a double-vote or preferential voting system.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Language Barriers:

Minority groups, who have little opportunity to produce political propaganda and campaign in their original language, struggle to reach their voters. Furthermore, just using the official language to prepare ballot papers and election materials has a detrimental impact on minorities' involvement in the political process.

Solution Proposals: Minority language promotion and campaigning rights should be allowed by election legislation modifications. Ballot papers and election materials should be created in many languages.

Limitation of Participation in Political Parties

Effects: Restrictions on political party formation and activity make it harder for minorities to form new parties or join existing ones.

Proposed Solutions: The political parties legislation should be modified to promote freedom of association and multiparty democracy. Minority groups' rights to form and run political parties should be safeguarded.

The Need for Reform in Election Law:

General Assessment: Electoral rules are the foundation of democratic representation. The fact that present rules exclude minorities from participating undermines democratic processes.

Proposed Solutions: Comprehensive election law changes are needed to achieve a fair and inclusive electoral system. These changes should include reducing election thresholds, rearranging electoral districts, and establishing measures to improve minority participation.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Increasing participation in political parties.

Integration into political parties and inclusive policies are critical for minorities' successful involvement in political processes.

Parties pursuing inclusive policies:

Effects: When political parties fail to integrate minorities' issues and demands in their policies, minority lose interest in the political process.

Solution Proposals: Parties should create inclusive policies that include the rights and needs of minorities in their programs. This will improve minorities' involvement in parties and political representation.

Inclusion of Minority Candidates in Lists

Effects: Failure to provide minority candidates enough space on election lists results in unequal representation.

Solution Proposals: Parties should provide minority candidates greater space on their electoral lists to boost their prospects of getting elected. Quotas, whether voluntary or legal, may be used for this purpose.

Political Education and Awareness Programs:

Effects: Minority groups' low levels of political knowledge and involvement lead to inferior representation.

Solution Proposals: Minority political involvement should be encouraged via education and

CURRENT SCIENCE

awareness campaigns in collaboration with civil society groups and political parties. These projects will help to build the democratic culture.

Promoting Diversity in the Party:

The absence of participation of minorities in party administration bodies means that their perspectives are not taken into consideration in decision-making processes. Solution Proposals: Parties should promote diversity within their internal structures and include members of minorities in management positions. This ensures that parties represent various elements of society.

Effectiveness of Legal Regulations

To safeguard and enhance the rights of minorities, legislative rules must be brought into line with international norms and successfully applied.

Compliance With International Agreements:

Effects: International accords to which Turkey and Azerbaijan are party establish commitments for the protection of minorities. However, the fact that these requirements are not completely represented in domestic law creates issues in practice.

Solution Proposals: Ensure that international accords are effectively translated and implemented into local law. The applicable articles of the UN Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, as well as the European Convention on Human Rights, should be considered. Constitutional and legal reforms:

Effects: Current constitutional and legal restrictions do not completely protect minorities' rights. Solution Proposals: Reorganize the constitution and legislation to preserve minorities' identities, cultures, and languages. Turkey should broaden the Treaty of Lausanne's concept of

CURRENT SCIENCE

a restricted minority and acknowledge the rights of all ethnic and religious communities. Similarly, rules protecting minority rights should be created in Azerbaijan.

Strengthening Implementation Mechanisms:

Effects: The failure to effectively apply legislative laws inhibits the practical protection of minority rights.

Solution Proposals: The independent judiciary and human rights institutions should be reinforced. Control systems should be strengthened, and rights breaches should be avoided.

Fighting Discrimination:

Effects: Discrimination and hate speech prohibit minorities from participating equally in social activities.

Solution Proposals: Anti-discrimination legislation should be implemented, and deterrent consequences should be imposed for such behavior. Social awareness should be raised via educational and awareness activities.

Supporting Civil Society and Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs):

Effects: Civil society groups play an essential role in safeguarding and advancing minority rights. However, when the operations of these groups are limited or blocked, minority' voices are silenced.

Solution Proposals: Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) should be permitted to function freely and supported by the state. Furthermore, international collaboration and the exchange of experiences should be promoted.

This section delves further into the procedures that must be taken and the solutions that have been presented to improve minorities' political rights. The analyses of minorities' political

CURRENT SCIENCE

representation, right to vote and be elected, participation in political parties, and the effectiveness of legal regulations are intended to contribute to the creation of a more inclusive and democratic political environment in Turkey and Azerbaijan. In this setting, political will and societal support are critical to implementing the recommended measures.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

This research carefully examined the reasons that impede minorities' political engagement in Turkey and Azerbaijan, revealing that comparable issues exist in both nations. Minorities' socioeconomic difficulties, a lack of protection for their language and cultural rights, and insufficient political representation all impede democratic processes from operating properly. The following specific policy proposals are made for the efficient use of minorities' political rights and a more inclusive democracy:

Reform the electoral system.

Lowering of election thresholds:

In Turkey, the existing 7% electoral threshold makes it difficult for minority groups and tiny parties to gain representation in parliament. Reducing or eliminating the electoral threshold would improve the fairness of representation.

In Azerbaijan, the election system has to be changed to provide for minority participation in parliament. Consider transitioning to a proportional representation system or improving the existing system.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Exceptions for minorities:

Election rules might provide special measures for minority parties or independent candidates to encourage their presence in parliament. This will result in more effective engagement of minorities in political processes.

Revision of the Political Party Law

Flexible Party Organization:

Laws governing the formation and activity of political parties should be amended to make it simpler for minorities to form their own parties and participate in political activities. Bureaucratic barriers to freedom of association should be eliminated.

Inclusive Party Policies:

Existing political parties' policies should address minorities' challenges and needs. Minority candidates should be given additional space on the ballots, and their presence at party administration levels should be guaranteed.

Educational and Awareness Programs

Political Rights Education:

Minorities' political rights should be promoted via educational initiatives. The young generation's knowledge of democracy and human rights may be improved via education in schools and civil society groups.

Awareness campaigns:

Using media and social platforms, society should be made more aware of minority rights and the richness of variety. These efforts will help reduce bigotry and prejudice.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Supporting Civil Society.

Promotion of Non-Governmental Organizations:

Civil society groups working on minority rights should be encouraged, and bureaucratic and legal barriers to their activity should be eliminated. NGOs' efficacy should be improved by giving financial and technical assistance.

Civil Society and Dynamics Cooperation:

Governments and civil society groups should build cooperation channels in order to better understand minorities' needs and aspirations and design policy appropriately.

Compliance with International Standards

Review of Legislation:

National law should be restructured to take into consideration international human rights accords and minority rights texts to which Turkey and Azerbaijan are signatories. The constitution and legislation should be aligned with international norms.
Activating the app:

To guarantee that legislative laws are effectively implemented in reality, control and monitoring systems should be developed. To avoid breaches of rights, the independent judiciary and human rights institutions should be reinforced.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Use of Technology

Supporting digital platforms:

Minorities should be encouraged to utilize digital platforms successfully so that they may connect with one another, promote their culture, and raise awareness of their concerns among a larger audience.

Increasing digital literacy:

Minority communities should get digital literacy training. Training on how to utilize technology effectively and safely should be offered, as well as internet access and infrastructure development.

Protection of Language and Cultural Rights.

Educational Opportunities in the Mother Tongue:
Legal and administrative procedures should be created to guarantee that minorities get education in their native language. The teaching and usage of minority languages in schools should be promoted.

Supporting Cultural Activities:

The state should encourage minorities' cultural activities and festivals. Cultural heritage protection and promotion projects should be established, and organizations working in this sector should be supported.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Economic and Social Development Programs

Investing In Minority Areas:

Investments should be made to promote economic growth in areas with a high concentration of minority populations. Employment possibilities should be expanded, infrastructure and social services should be improved, and regional disparities addressed.

Fighting Discrimination:

Legal restrictions must be adequately applied to avoid discrimination in business and public services. Discrimination should be punished severely, and the concept of equality should be upheld.

Human Rights Watch (HRW). (2023). Report on Minorities' Rights in Turkey and Azerbaijan.

Amnesty International. (2022). Azerbaijan: Ethnic Minorities and Human Rights.

This essay examines the current situation in Turkey and Azerbaijan regarding minorities' political rights and makes tangible policy proposals for a more inclusive democracy. Minority political engagement must be increased in order for not just minority groups but for society as a whole to progress democratically.

References

Acemoğlu, D., Egorov, G., & Sonin, K. (2015, September 10). Political Economy in a Changing World. University of Chicago Press, 123(5), 1038-1086.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/682679>

- Aydın S. (2021). Minorities' Political Participation and Representation Problems in Turkey. Ankara University Faculty of Political Sciences Journal, 76(2), 345–372.
- Mammadov, R. (2022). Azerbaijan's Minority Policies in Light of European Integration. Caucasus Studies Journal, 15(1), 89–115.

Current Academic Articles and NGO Reports:

Data from the Azerbaijan State Statistics Committee.

Demir, O. (2017, June 30). THE FATE OF HATAY PROVINCE, BETWEEN TURKEY AND SYRIA. , 37-46. <https://doi.org/10.18662/jls/3>

Düzgit, S A., & Keyman, F. (2012, December 4). EU-Turkey relations and the stagnation of Turkish democracy. http://ipc.sabanciuniv.edu/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/GTE_WP_02.pdf

EU-Turkey Relations and the Stagnation of Turkish Democracy. (n.d). http://research.sabanciuniv.edu/23576/1/GTE_WP_02.pdf

Hughes, E. (2008, January 1). The Secularism Debate and Turkey's Quest for European Union Membership. Brill, 3(1), 15-32. <https://doi.org/10.1163/187103108x286528>

İlkkaracan, P. (1998, January 1). Exploring the context of women's sexuality in Eastern Turkey. Taylor & Francis, 6(12), 66-75. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0968-8080\(98\)90009-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0968-8080(98)90009-x)

İnce, B. (2012, February 24). Citizenship education in Turkey: inclusive or exclusive. Taylor & Francis, 38(2), 115-131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2011.651314>

Journal of Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Economics and Administrative Sciences Faculty. (2023, February 27). <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/makuiibf/issue/41626>

Kilbas, A A., Srivastava, H M., & Trujillo, J J. (2006, January 1). Preface. Elsevier BV, vii-x. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-0208\(06\)80001-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-0208(06)80001-0)

Kılıç, A. (2008, July 8). The Gender Dimension of Social Policy Reform in Turkey: Towards Equal Citizenship?. Wiley, 42(5), 487-503. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9515.2008.00620.x>

Kitap Tanıtım ve Değerlendirmesi. (2015, June 25). https://www.academia.edu/13272596/Kitap_Tan%C4%B1t%C4%B1m_ve_De%C4%9Ferlendirmesi

Köksal, D. (2001, September 1). Fine-Tuning Nationalism: Critical Perspectives from Republican Literature in Turkey. Taylor & Francis, 2(2), 63-84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/714005687>

Kymlicka, W. (1995). Multicultural Citizenship: A Liberal Approach to Minority Rights. Oxford University Press.

Lijphart, A. (1999). Patterns of Democracy: Government Forms and Performance in 36 Countries. Yale University Press.

Ross, C J. (2009, January 1). Perennial Outsiders: The Educational Experience of Turkish Youth in Germany. Springer Nature (Netherlands), 24(5). <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/auilr/vol24/iss5/4/>

Simple, intelligent, modern content sending. (n.d). <https://docsend.com/view/ww5ipvs>

Sorunlu Bolgelerde Goc-Migration in Conflict Areas. (2008, January 1). https://www.academia.edu/15217802/Sorunlu_Bolgelerde_Goc_Migration_in_Conflict_Areas

Taylor, C. (1994). Multiculturalism: Investigating the Politics of Recognition. Princeton University Press.

The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

The Constitution of the Republic of Turkey.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The European Convention on Human Rights.

The Turkish Statistical Institute (TurkStat) provides official statistics.

The UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Toktaş, Ş. (2005, November 16). Citizenship and Minorities: A Historical Overview of Turkey's Jewish Minority. Wiley, 18(4), 394-429. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6443.2005.00262.x>

Tuna, T. (2012, October 23). Gender and Modernization in Turkey. , 2(5), 273-273. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijld.v2i5.2554>

Ulusoy, K. (2009, September 1). Europeanization and Political Change: The Case of Cyprus. Taylor & Francis, 10(3), 393-408. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683840903141715>